

Non-Fatal Opioid Overdose and Major Depression among Street-Recruited Young Heroin Users

Marcela Chahua^a Luis Sordo^{b, c, g} Gregorio Barrio^{a, c} Antonia Domingo-Salvany^{c, e}
M. Teresa Brugal^{c, d, f} Gemma Molist^{b, c} Luis de la Fuente^{b, c} María J. Bravo^{b, c}
and ITINERE Project Group

^aEscuela Nacional de Sanidad and ^bCentro Nacional de Epidemiología Instituto de Salud Carlos III, and

^cCIBER Epidemiología y Salud Pública (CIBERESP), Madrid, ^dInstitut d'Investigació Biomèdica (IB Sant Pau),

^ePrograma Epidemiología y Salud Pública, IMIM-Hospital del Mar, and ^fAgència de Salut Pública de Barcelona, Barcelona,

^gDepartment of Preventive Medicine and Public Health, Faculty of Medicine, Complutense University, Madrid, Spain

Key Words

Non-fatal opioid overdose · Major depression · Heroin users · Epidemiology

Abstract

Background/Aims: Non-fatal opioid overdose (NFOO) and major depression (MD) are highly prevalent in heroin users. Many risk factors are known for NFOO, but studies in non-clinical samples on its relationship with MD are lacking. We aimed to examine this relationship in a street-recruited sample, controlling for potential well-known confounders.

Methods: A cross-sectional study in 452 heroin users street-recruited by chain referral methods in three Spanish cities. Eligibility criteria were: age ≤ 30 years, heroin use at least 12 days in the last year and at least once in the last 3 months. Depression was assessed using the Composite International Diagnostic Interview. A precise definition of NFOO was used. Adjusted odds ratios (AORs) for the NFOO predictors were obtained by logistic regression. **Results:** The prevalence of NFOO and MD in the last 12 months was 9.1 and 23.2%, respectively. After adjusting for potential confounders, NFOO and MD were significantly associated (AOR 2.2; 95% CI 1.01-

4.74). Other associated factors were imprisonment (AOR 4.1; 95% CI 1.4-12.1), drug injection (AOR 6.7; 95% CI 2.4-18.4) and regular use of tranquillisers/sleeping pills (AOR 2.9; 95% CI 1.16-7). **Conclusions:** Drug and mental health treatment facilities should consider the relationship between MD and NFOO when contacting and treating heroin users. Imprisonment, drug injection and use of tranquillisers/sleeping pills are also risk factors for NFOO.

Introduction

Opioid overdose is a leading cause of death among opioid users in the European Union [1]. One study has reported that approximately 3.1% of overdose events among heroin users result in death [2], and major depres-

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sion (MD) among drug users also appears to involve a considerable mortality risk [3]. It is also known that both non-fatal opioid overdose (NFOO) and MD are highly prevalent among opioid users [4–7]. In addition, both NFOO and MD are preventable and modifiable conditions [2, 3] that share some common risk factors such as intensive opioid use [7, 8], problematic use of benzodiazepines, tranquillisers or psychoactive drugs other than opioids [8, 9], illegal drug injection [7, 10], or HIV infection [11]. Conversely, methadone maintenance treatment (MMT) is protective against opioid overdose [12, 14], and MD improves among methadone patients [13].

The relationship between MD and NFOO could be highly relevant in the reduction of opioid overdose occurrence; nevertheless, the number of studies is small and the results controversial. They vary in the pattern of participants' drug use, the definition of overdose, and the scale used to measure depression. To our knowledge the majority of studies are based on clinical samples, and only one of them [10] has exclusively been carried out among street-recruited heroin users. This study found an association between depressive symptoms and overdose in the last 12 months in a sample of 729 street-recruited drug users in the USA, although the study [10] did not specifically define opioid overdose. A positive association was also found in a clinical sample of detoxification patients in the same country [16]. However, a clinical study in Australia between 2004 and 2008 that aimed to compare correlates of lifetime suicide attempts and lifetime unintentional NFOO did not find an association between unintentional NFOO and depression [17]. A previous study which compared a clinical sample with a group of non-treatment heroin users in order to assess changes in the patterns of depression and related outcomes also failed to find a relationship between recent MD and recent NFOO [18]. Another Australian study in a smaller and poorly defined sample of ever heroin users found a higher lifetime prevalence of overdose among participants with depressive symptoms [19]. Our objective was to determine if recent diagnosis of MD is independently associated with recent NFOO among street-recruited young heroin users in three major Spanish cities, taking into account potential well-known confounders.

Methods

Subjects

This study analysed a subsample of the 'ITINERE' cohort of heroin users. A total of 991 participants were recruited in this cohort. In order to obtain a sample of young, regular heroin users

with a minimum intensity of use that could involve some health problems, the recruitment criteria were defined as age 30 years or younger and having used heroin for at least 12 days in the last 12 months and at least 1 day in the last 3 months. The sample was street-recruited in Madrid, Barcelona and Seville by targeted sampling [20] and incentive-driven methods as a modified approach of respondent-driven sampling [21]. The first seeds in the chain were directly recruited by an anthropologist and social workers belonging to the research team who visited open settings or public venues where the target group congregated. These research team members also recruited a few paid key drug-using informers who helped with the seeds recruitment. The rest of the sample was recruited by chain-referral methods that combined rewards for being interviewed (EUR 18) with nomination of other participants (EUR 10 once the person nominated completed his/her participation in the study). Recruitment from drug treatment services was avoided. The interviews took place in health and social centres (medical or nursing consultations, social work departments, neighbourhood or district social centres, etc.). The questionnaire was applied by trained interviewers not belonging to the centres. There were two follow-up visits [22].

The mental health section of the questionnaire was not ready to be applied at intake and was introduced in the questionnaire when the first follow-up assessment had already started in a certain proportion of participants. Thus, the scale used to measure depression was answered by 561 subjects at the first or second follow-up visits between 2002 and 2005, which means that 431 (43%) of the participants had been lost during follow-up. The cross-sectional analysis of this study ultimately included 452 participants, because 109 of those answering the depression scale had not used opioids during the last 12 months and consequently were eliminated from the analysis. An informed consent document was signed by the participants.

Data Collection and Measures

A pre-coded questionnaire was applied during a computer-assisted personal interview. Depression was assessed with the World Mental Health Composite International Diagnostic Interview (CIDI) [23], which has proved to be both reliable and valid [24]. Recent MD within the last 12 months was defined according to DSM-IV criteria. With current drug users it is possible that some reported symptoms are produced by drug use or withdrawal rather than being caused by MD, however the CIDI specifically probes for drug effects and excludes symptoms that appear to be related exclusively to drug use [18].

Other measures were: major sociodemographic characteristics, imprisonment or having been arrested, frequency and number of days of use of cocaine or heroin, cocaine binges, tranquillisers/sleeping pills use, alcohol use, NFOO, drug injection and syringe sharing, MMT, as well as attendance to any type of treatment. Use of alcohol was rated as none or moderate (<40 g/day for men and <20 g/day for women), or at risk (≥40 g/day for men and ≥20 g/day for women). To avoid participants possibly misunderstanding NFOO as some other acute problem occurring after consumption of a psychoactive substance, recent NFOO was precisely defined in the questionnaire as 'an episode occurring after opioid use (heroin, methadone, other opioids such as "buprex", "sosegon", "deprancol", "morphine", etc.) and characterised by extreme difficulty in breathing, loss of consciousness and problems waking up or recovering consciousness, and possibly bluish skin or lips' in the

12 months before the interview. The following clarification was also included 'Please keep in mind that we are not interested in overdoses due to cocaine, amphetamines or ecstasy, which are usually accompanied by hot flushed skin or fever, tachycardia, nervousness, anxiety and sometimes convulsions.'

Determination of antibodies in the dried blood samples was made for anti-HIV and anti-HCV [22]. Commercial enzyme-linked immunosorbent analyses (ELISAs) were used to determine antibodies against HIV (ELISA Genscreen HIV1/2 version 2; Bio-Rad, Marnes-la-Coquette, France) and HCV (Monolisa anti-HCV plus version 2; Bio-Rad). Reactive samples were re-analysed and were considered positive only if they showed double reactivity.

Data Analysis

A bivariate analysis was performed to obtain the prevalence of NFOO by depression status and by the categories of other possible risk factors. χ^2 and Fisher's exact tests were used to assess the statistical significance of differences between proportions, using a significance level of 0.05 in two-tailed tests. A logistic regression model was fitted to assess the relationship between overdose and depression. Those variables found to be associated ($p < 0.05$) with NFOO in the bivariate analysis were included in the multivariate model. Potential confounders identified in other studies – sex, age, frequency of heroin use [7, 8], use of benzodiazepines, tranquillisers or use of other psychoactive drugs [8, 9, 25], drug injection [7, 8, 10], HIV serostatus [11] and MMT attendance [7, 12–14] – were also considered for inclusion in the model even if they were not associated in our bivariate analysis. A sensitivity analysis was then performed including only those variables found to be associated in the bivariate analysis. Crude (OR) and adjusted (AOR) odds ratios and their corresponding 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) were obtained as measures of the strength of association.

Results

Of the 452 participants, 26.9% were women, 32% were younger than 25 years (mean age 26 years, SD 3.25), 36.7% had primary or lower level education, 25.7% were employed, 21.2% were homeless (defined as having been living most of the time on the street, in abandoned houses or in similar places), 8% had been in prison in the 12 months, and 54.7% had been arrested in that period. About 58.4% had a stable partner and 29.6% had children.

With respect to patterns of drug and treatment-services use in the last 12 months, 30.2 and 38% had used heroin or cocaine, respectively, five or more times per week, 44.3% had had a cocaine binge, 60.9% had consumed heroin, mainly by smoking, 53.5% had injected drugs (19.1% of whom had shared needles or syringes), 32.4% were risk drinkers, 38.5% took tranquillisers/sleeping pills ≥ 3 days/week, 37.6% had been in methadone treatment, and 14.6% had received another type of drug treatment. The prevalence of anti-HIV and anti-HCV positive

serostatus was 20.8 and 52%, respectively. For all the variables described that are not shown in table 1, the non-response rate was 2.7% or less.

The recent prevalence of NFOO and MD was 9.1 and 23.2%, respectively. In the bivariate analysis, NFOO prevalence was higher among those who had had a depressive episode than among those who had not (15.2 vs. 7.2%, $p = 0.01$). In addition, a significant association with NFOO was found for age ($p < 0.05$) and other recent conditions, such as imprisonment ($p < 0.05$), tranquillisers/sleeping pills use ≥ 3 days/week ($p < 0.05$), homelessness ($p < 0.05$), unemployment ($p < 0.05$) and drug injection ($p < 0.01$) (table 1). Recent NFOO remained independently associated in the multivariate logistic analysis with recent MD after adjusting for factors significantly associated in the bivariate analysis and for other potential confounders (AOR 2.2; 95% CI 1.01–4.74). Other independently associated factors were recent imprisonment (AOR 4.1; 95% CI 1.4–12.1), drug injection (AOR 6.7; 95% CI 2.4–18.4) and use of tranquillisers/sleeping pills ≥ 3 days/week (AOR 2.9; 95% CI 1.16–7) (table 1). The results of a sensitivity analysis including only the variables found to be associated in the bivariate analysis showed no relevant differences in the estimates of association between NFOO and MD (AOR 2.16; 95% CI 1.06–4.39).

Discussion

We found that recent occurrence of NFOO was associated with recent MD among street-recruited young regular heroin users. This association remained after adjustment for age, sex, drug injection, imprisonment, homelessness, frequency of heroin use, tranquillisers/sleeping pills use, alcohol consumption, MMT attendance and HIV serostatus. Those with recent MD were over twice as likely to have suffered a NFOO in the same period.

Our findings confirm the results of the only previous study that to our knowledge also examined the association between depressive symptoms and overdose in a sample of street-recruited drug users [10], however our study more specifically addressed the topic of opioid overdose and was particularly careful to clarify the definition of overdose given to the participants. The existence of only one previous study also conducted among street-recruited drug users is probably due to the logistic difficulties involved in applying a long validated questionnaire such as the CIDI outside a clinical setting. In our case, the questionnaire was applied by trained interviewers in settings not related with either drug treatment or

Table 1. Bi- and multivariate analysis of factors associated with NFOO in the last 12 months among young heroin users (n = 452)

Independent variable		NFOO		OR	95% CI	AOR	95% CI
		yes n (%)	no n (%)				
Depression ^a	No	25 (61)	322 (78.3)	1		1	
	Yes	16 (39)	89 (21.7)	2.32*	1.19–4.52	2.2*	1.01–4.74
Age	<25	19 (46.3)	125 (30.7)	1		1	
	≥25	22 (53.7)	282 (69.3)	0.51*	0.27–0.98	0.6	0.28–1.32
Sex	Male	26 (63.4)	304 (74)	1		1	
	Female	15 (36.6)	107 (26)	1.64	0.84–3.21	1.27	0.58–2.81
Prison ^a	No	34 (82.6)	378 (92.9)	1		1	
	Yes	7 (17.4)	29 (7.1)	2.68*	1.09–6.58	4.08**	1.38–12.08
Homeless ^{a,b}	No	27 (65.8)	329 (80)	1		1	
	Yes	14 (34.2)	82 (20)	2.1*	1.05–4.14	1.07	0.45–2.52
Employment ^a	Yes	5 (12.2)	111 (27)	1		1	
	No	36 (77.8)	300 (73)	2.66*	1.02–6.96	1.94	0.68–5.52
Drug injection ^a	No	5 (12.2)	205 (49.9)	1		1	
	Yes	36 (77.8)	206 (50.1)	7.16**	2.76–18.62	6.75**	2.45–18.44
Heroin use ^a	<5 days/week	27 (65.8)	280 (70.2)	1		1	
	≥5 days/week	14 (34.2)	119 (19.8)	1.22	0.62–2.41	1.61	0.72–3.59
Cocaine use ^a	None	1 (2.5)	12 (3)	1		1	
	<5 days/week	24 (58.5)	240 (59.1)	1.2	0.16–53.41	1.44	0.16–13.07
	≥5 days/week	16 (39)	154 (37.9)	1.25	0.16–56.58	1.18	0.56–2.5
Tranquillisers/sleeping pills ^a	None	7 (17.1)	110 (26.7)	1		1	
	<3 days/week	9 (21.9)	152 (37)	0.93	0.29–3	1.77	0.59–5.35
	3 or more days/week	25 (61)	149 (36.3)	2.64*	1.1–6.32	2.86*	1.16–7.02
Alcohol use ^{a,c}	None	7 (17.1)	94 (22.9)	1		1	
	Yes, moderate	18 (43.9)	173 (42.1)	1.4	0.53–4.1	1.54	0.53–4.44
	Yes, risk	16 (39)	144 (35)	1.49	0.59–3.76	2.38	0.84–6.69
Methadone maintenance treatment ^a	No	22 (53.7)	213 (51.8)	1		1	
	Yes	16 (39)	154 (37.5)	1	0.5–1.98	1.51	0.68–3.35
	Unknown	3 (7.3)	44 (10.7)	0.66	0.18–2.3	0.79	0.17–3.55
HIV-positive	No	29 (70.7)	318 (80.1)	1		1	
	Yes	12 (29.3)	79 (19.9)	1.66	0.81–3.41	1.59	0.69–3.69

^a Refers to the last 12 months. ^b Living most of the time on the street, in abandoned houses or in similar places. ^c Alcohol use: moderate (<40 g/day for men and <20 g/day for women); risk (≥40 g/day for men and ≥20 g/day for women). OR and AOR using multivariate logistic regression: * p < 0.05 ** p < 0.01. All variables included in the multivariate model are presented in the table.

224 harm reduction facilities in order to avoid social desirability bias. Bums et al. [19] also found results similar to ours and those of Tobin and Latkin [10], but considering lifetime period experience of NFOO and MD [19]; the study, however, suffered from some methodological drawbacks such as a very small sample of heroin users and the use of 'self-reported levels of depression' instead of a

224 validated scale of MD. The study of Wines et al. [16] also found an association between overdose and depressive symptoms among detoxification patients, who may have been highly vulnerable to overdose due to a reduced tolerance to heroin. In addition, the definition of non-fatal overdose also involved a lack of specificity as the term was applicable to any drug with overdose risk.

239 Conversely, no association was found between MD and
240 'heroin overdose' in two studies among population groups
241 different from ours; the first included both heroin users
242 entering treatment for heroin dependence and others not
243 in treatment [18], and the second was based on a large
244 sample of opioid-dependent individuals recruited from
245 public and private MMT facilities [17]. In the latter study,
246 both MD and NFOO were assessed as lifetime events.
247 In our study, both MD and NFOO events were studied in the
248 same recall period – recent – and this circumstance, al-
249 though in a cross-sectional study, should be considered a
250 strength in comparison to those assessing lifetime events.
251 In addition, our study used a very precise definition of
252 opioid overdose among heroin users, who, as has frequently
253 been found in other studies, were also heavy users of
254 cocaine or other drugs. It is often the case in research on
255 fatal overdose that the definitions or description of the
256 typical symptoms of overdose are described poorly [10, 16, 17,
257 19, 26], or not at all in the article [18]. A minimum
258 requirement in self-reported non-fatal overdose/NFOO
259 studies should always be to provide participants with a
260 clear and precise description of these events. 311

261 Consistent with other studies among heroin users, we
262 also found a substantial prevalence of MD and NFOO [13,
263 7, 27]. Although there are no sound estimates of overdose
264 lethality, it appears that the ratio of non-fatal heroin over-
265 dose to fatal heroin overdose may be around 31:1 [2].
266 That MD is associated with a 20-fold increased risk of com-
267 pleted suicide in different drug-using populations [13].
268 Some authors have hypothesised that a large proportion
269 of heroin overdoses are wrongly classified as suicides [28,
270 29], that overdose mortality and suicides are different
271 clinical matters [4], and that NFOO and suicide attempts
272 have different correlates [17]. In our study, unfortunately,
273 we cannot rule out that the relation between overdose and
274 depression could be mediated by suicide attempts, as has
275 been suggested by others [30]. Nevertheless, we should
276 emphasise the difficulties of such studies in relying either
277 on self-reports for the intentionality of overdoses or
278 NFOO as an attempt of suicide; it is uncertain whether
279 people might be reluctant to admit they were seeking
280 death. On the other hand, it cannot be ruled out that
281 factors associated with NFOO might be different from
282 those related to fatal opioid overdose, and that the oppor-
283 tunity to report a NFOO may even imply that the opioid
284 overdoses in these heroin users are less lethal or fatal (lower
285 lethality or case-fatality ratio). Nevertheless, research
286 findings support the view that a great number of overdose
287 risk factors are common for both fatal and NFOO [13],
288 such as injection, reduced tolerance, use of benzodiazepines
289 and heroin use, as has been observed in people with non-ar-

290 pines, use of alcohol, or not being in methadone treatment
[4]. Risk factors that are different for NFOO and fatal
overdose would likely be those related with easy access to
safer injection facilities [27] or naloxone treatment [31].
Whether the relationship between depression and NFOO
is also applicable to fatal overdose should remain an objec-
tive of future research, although it very likely is.

In addition, our study found a strong association be-
tween MD and other factors, such as imprisonment,
drug injection and use of tranquillisers/sleeping pills.
The ORs for these factors were even higher than for MD.
There is no controversy about the role of release from
prison in deaths from overdose [32] or having ever been
in prison and NFOO [9], which is consistent with our
finding. This is a well-known risk factor, and WHO has
recently released a specific document on this issue to im-
prove overdose prevention [33]. On the other hand, in-
jection is known to be a risk factor for opioid overdose
[4]; in a crossover analysis, the relative risk for injecting
heroin versus other routes of administration immedi-
ately before overdose was 15.9, which is also highly con-
sistent with our results [8]. The use of tranquillisers/sleep-
ing pills is one of the earliest identified risk factors for
overdose [8, 25, 34]. The excess risk of overdose found in
our study among those who consumed tranquillisers/
sleeping pills ≥ 3 days/week, even after controlling for
factors like depression and drug-dependence treatment,
should be studied in greater depth to determine the effect
of using these substances on the risk of overdose, both
when they are and are not medically prescribed [25].

It is worth noting that, although MMT has been found
to be a protective factor for opioid overdose [12–14] and is
associated with improvements in depression [15], in our
study, the prevalence of NFOO among those who were in
MMT did not differ from those who were not. Unfortu-
nately, as we lacked information about MMT discontinu-
ation or MMT duration, we cannot rule out that these
might have been factors hindering the benefits of MMT on
overdose, although it has been shown that MMT retention
rates are not lower among MMT patients with psychiatric
co-morbidity [35]. Our results may also suggest that MD
was not dealt with appropriately during MMT or that

MMT services do not specifically address overdose preven-
tion. On the other hand, it would be interesting to investi-
gate if other medications for substitution, i.e. morphine or
diamorphine [36], would be able to reduce NFOO, espe-
cially because diamorphine has been shown to be very ef-
fective in suppressing the stress response and craving [37].
Some studies have found that depression is not the
only mental disorder that appears to be closely related to
fictive disorders [38, 39]. Substance users with psychiat-

342 ric co-morbidity present greater disorder severity from
343 both the clinical and social perspectives than those diag-
344 nosed with only one type of disorder, such as greater stig-
345 matisation or discrimination [38]. The quality of inte-
346 grated care for these patients needs to be improved in
347 order to effectively merge contemporary separated
348 teams into one therapeutic team – the mental health and
349 substance-user care networks [40].

350 It is difficult to compare the characteristics of our sam-
351 ple with other recent studies in Spain, mainly due to our
352 selection criteria with regard to the age limitation and type
353 of sampling. There are only two studies [41, 42] that would
354 allow some comparison, although in both cases they in-
355 cluded only drug injectors, one in 1998 (n = 1,638) [41] and
356 the other in 2004 (n = 300) [42]. The sociodemographic
357 characteristics of participants in both of these studies (age,
358 unemployment and homelessness) were similar to our
359 findings, however the mean age was >30 years, clearly
360 higher than in our study. As expected, the mean age among
361 the 33,702 persons admitted to outpatient drug treatment
362 centres for heroin abuse or dependence in 2001 in Spain
363 (31.4 years) was also higher than found in our study, while
364 the level of unemployment was lower (52.6%) [43].

365 In addition to the fact that our study was cross-sectional,
366 which means that we cannot make causal inferences,
367 other study limitations are: (a) We do not know how repre-
368 sentative our sample is since it was not randomly se-
369 lected; nevertheless, efforts were made to make the sam-
370 ple as representative as possible by mapping all probable
371 recruitment settings through ethnographic methodology
372 and an active search for most types of hidden heroin users
373 (those that are socially integrated, very young, recent
374 drug users, etc.). (b) Our data did not permit the identifi-
375 cation of suicide attempts or intentional overdose.

376 Data on other possible confounders such as antidepressant
377 use or MMT treatment duration were not available.
378 (d) Although we controlled for well-known potential
379 confounders, the relationship between MD and NFOO
380 could be affected by some residual confounding due to
381 factors for which we had no information and which could
382 be distributed differently in other populations of young
383 heroin users. Consequently, even though the relationship
384 also exists in other populations of heroin users, any ex-
385 trapolation of the findings should be made with caution.
386 Our study supports that imprisonment, drug injection
387 and regular use of tranquillisers/sleeping pills are relevant
388 risk factors for NFOO. More importantly, our findings are
389 an important contribution to a poorly studied issue, which

is the confirmation of a statistically significant association
between recent MD and recent NFOO, taking into ac-
count some potential confounders. Both MD and NFOO
are two modifiable conditions with an important public
health impact. This association should be considered by
MMT and mental health facilities when treating heroin
users with either depression or other known risk factors
for opioid overdose. More research is needed on how to
design effective interventions for overdose prevention
among those opioid users suffering a depressive disorder.

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